

White Paper ID Number	W006
Title of White Paper	Science, Technical and Strategic benefits of Canadian partnership with Subaru
ID of Associated Expression of Interest	E006
Topic Area of White Paper	new facilities, experiments and missions

Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Recent developments have opened up an opportunity to join the Subaru telescope under favourable terms. With the demonstrated success of SCEXAO and HSC, and first light of the PFS nearly upon us, the immediate prospects for Subaru to make breakthrough discoveries that align well with Canadian interests are excellent. In this white paper we describe the scientific and technical (instrumentation) opportunities that a partnership with Subaru would enable. We highlight the important synergies with TMT, MSE and Euclid, and how a relatively small investment in Subaru can significantly enhance our ability to take advantage of those facilities. In particular, access to PFS in the decade before MSE sees first light will be critical for ensuring Canadians have the technical and scientific expertise to fully exploit, and lead, science with that next generation spectroscopic facility. The partnership also has strategic value, as it represents an important step toward building an alliance of observatories on Maunakea, which itself has the potential for dramatically increasing scientific impact and reducing costs.

Lead author and affiliation Michael Balogh, University of Waterloo

Email address of lead author mbalogh@uwaterloo.ca

Other authors and affiliations

Marcin Sawicki, Ivana Damjanov (SMU)
Stephane Courteau (Queens)
Howard Yee, Bob Abraham, Jo Bovy, Maria Drout, Suresh Sivanandam, Dae-Sik Moon (UofT)
Adam Muzzin (York)
Laura Parker (McMaster)
Mike Hudson, Will Percival (Waterloo)
Jan Cami (Western)
Chris O'Dea (Manitoba)
Jeremy Heyl, Ludo van Waerbeke (UBC)
Sara Ellison, Jon Willis, Kim Venn, Colin Bradley (UVic)
Tracy Webb (McGill)
Alan McConnachie, Christian Marois, JJ Kavelaars, Laura Ferrarese, Pat Cote, Stephen Gwyn, Luc Simard (NRC)
Rene Doyon, David Lafreniere (U de Montreal)

1 Leadership in Optical/Infrared Astronomy

At optical/IR wavelengths, Canada has long enjoyed significant access to two of the most competitive observatories on the planet: CFHT (3.6m) and Gemini (two 8-m telescopes). These facilities are complementary, in part because CFHT is capable of imaging a wide field, while Gemini is the preferred facility for deep, high resolution images and spectroscopy over small fields. With CFHT, Canada was once a world leader and innovator in the wide-field survey science that now dominates the landscape. In particular, with spectroscopic surveys like CNOG (Yee et al., 1996) and CFRS (Lilly et al., 1996), Canadians took advantage of CFHT's MOS, which was then the state-of-the-art wide-field multiobject spectrograph, to make transformative breakthroughs in our understanding of cosmology and galaxy formation. This leadership continued with the CFHT Legacy Survey, enabled by the largest imager in the world at that time, MegaCam.

CFHT has managed to remain competitive in the era of 8-m class telescopes, partly because there is only one telescope in that larger class that is capable of imaging a wide field: *Subaru*. In addition, the exquisite image quality and u-band sensitivity of CFHT has allowed it to retain a unique niche, that has been exploited with the new Canada-France Imaging Survey (CFIS, Ibata et al., 2017), a national-level survey on a scale that has not been seen since the days of CFHTLS. Most importantly, CFIS has enabled Canadians to leverage access to Euclid data, and to form a partnership with Pan-STARRS that has resulted in the UNIONS collaboration - a *ugriz* imaging survey¹ of most of the northern sky.

Despite this success, in most respects imaging capabilities on CFHT are inferior to those of Hyper Suprime-Cam (HSC) on Subaru, and will soon be made largely irrelevant by LSST (except for the northern hemisphere access) and Euclid. While Canada has the potential to play an important role in both Euclid and LSST, these are initiatives led by other players (Europe and the US, respectively). Our late, non-hardware contributions limit the opportunity for a leadership role, though it is still possible to head innovative science projects. Wide field, deep optical imaging in the northern hemisphere will continue to be dominated by Subaru.

In addition, CFHT no longer has a wide-field spectroscopy capability, and such a capability would struggle to be competitive given instruments like DESI (DESI Collaboration et al., 2016), WEAVE (Dalton et al., 2012), MOONS (Cirasuolo et al., 2012), 4MOST (Haynes et al., 2014), and PFS (see § 2.2, below). For these reasons Canada is leading the effort to transform CFHT into the Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer (MSE), an 11-m, dedicated spectroscopic survey facility. At present, construction of this facility is unfunded, and first light is most likely to come no sooner than the end of the 2020s decade. Critically, we have no national (and few individual) prospects for getting involved in wide-field spectroscopy before that time, leaving a significant gap in scientific discovery, training and recruitment that will have a long term impact on our community. This gap will make it very challenging for Canadians to continue to lead the technical development of MSE and its subsequent scientific exploitation.

2 Subaru

Subaru is the flagship observatory of the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ), and saw first light in 1999. It benefits from excellent image quality as it is sited at the best location in the northern hemisphere, the summit of Maunakea. As noted above, it is the only 8-m class telescope capable of wide field imaging. The telescope has hosted numerous sensitive instruments since its construction, but at present has a focused, highly successful instrumentation program built upon wide field imaging (HSC), wide field spectroscopy (Prime Focus Spectrograph, PFS) and high contrast imaging (SCEXAO).

2.1 Suprime-Cam and Hyper Suprime-Cam

Suprime-Cam was a $34' \times 27'$ field optical camera, with a pixel scale of $0.20''$. It has since been replaced by HSC, which covers a circular field 1.5 degrees in diameter. These instruments have been very successful: 325 papers, collectively cited over 11,000 times, mention these instruments in their abstracts. They have had a big impact on

¹The *g*-band component is being obtained with Subaru, via Gemini exchange time and the Hawaii TAC; a Japanese collaboration is proposing a new Subaru program to complete the *z*-band portion.

our understanding of high redshift galaxies and AGN (Kong et al., 2006; Ouchi et al., 2008; Matsuoka et al., 2016; Ono et al., 2018), cosmology (Hamana et al., 2003; Graur et al., 2011; Niikura et al., 2019), galactic archaeology (McConnachie et al., 2007; Aoki et al., 2009; Lamb et al., 2017), galaxy clusters (Kodama et al., 2001; Umetsu et al., 2014) and low surface brightness galaxies (Koda et al., 2015; Kovács et al., 2019). The ongoing 300-night HSC Subaru Strategic Program (HSC SSP, Aihara et al., 2018) promises to further magnify this impact by providing a public dataset of unprecedented depth and area.

2.2 Prime Focus Spectrograph

Currently under construction, Subaru PFS is a wide field (1.3 degree diameter) multifiber spectrograph, perfectly designed for spectroscopic follow-up of HSC's imaging surveys. PFS has been of interest to many Canadians for years. It grew out of the [WF MOS](#) concept (Smee et al., 2006), which Canadians were instrumental in developing. Initially envisioned as an instrument mounted at Gemini's Prime Focus, a partnership with Subaru was later considered where WF MOS would be mounted on Subaru but operate as a Gemini instrument. When this arrangement failed, due to insufficient funding of the Gemini "Aspen" instrumentation program, PFS emerged, supported by a large international consortium of institutions that, however, includes no Canadians. The PFS consortium will have an allocation of several hundred guaranteed nights in return for providing the instrument, and this will be used to conduct one or more large surveys that are now being prepared through the Subaru Strategic Programs (SSP). However, PFS will be available to proposals from the whole Subaru community, and will become a NAOJ-owned facility instrument at the conclusion of the initial PFS SSP(s). A group of Canadians has tried on several occasions to obtain funding to join PFS and the associated SSP, for example via a CFI application to provide software development, but these efforts were not successful.

2.3 SCEXAO

SCEXAO is one of the few dedicated high-contrast imaging spectrograph instruments worldwide. Its main science goals are the imaging discovery and characterization of the thermal near-infrared light of exoplanets and disks around nearby young stars. In contrast to facility-class instruments such as the Gemini Planet Imager (GPI) and SPHERE, SCEXAO is using a fast track development process to rapidly deploy state-of-the-art technologies. It is, in many ways, a pathfinder to validate new technologies in an actual "on sky" environment. Using the corrected wavefront from the Subaru AO188 adaptive optics system, SCEXAO currently showcases a high-order deformable mirror, a set of different coronagraphic focal plane masks and shape pupils, an integral field spectrograph (CHARIS) and a fast KHz photon counting visible camera (VAMPIRES). Many more modes are under development, including a MKIDS camera, a set of interferometers and high-resolution spectroscopic systems. SCEXAO currently achieves GPI-like performance on sky; with planned upgrades, it is expected to perform a GPI-/SPHERE-like campaign in the next few years but achieving deeper contrast, especially at small angles. Many Canadian astronomers have great interest in SCEXAO, with some having secured time to perform a small campaign by using the Gemini-Subaru time exchange program. The few hours available to Canadians each semester through the time exchange program does severely restrict the scope of these Canadian led campaigns. The SCEXAO team has shown itself to be enthusiastically supportive of Canadian involvement in future instrument developments, in science programs and in sharing expertise in data reduction. SCEXAO, with his modular approach, would be one of the best instrument to validate Canadian high-contrast technologies for future deployment as TMT instruments, such as the FAST (Gerard et al., 2018) focal plane wavefront method. It also offers the opportunity to use a vast array of unique capabilities to perform breakthrough discoveries. There is Canadian interest in joining the SCEXAO campaign science team for the upcoming exoplanet/disk campaign.

2.4 Future instrumentation

There is a strong drive at NAOJ to develop a ground-layer adaptive optics (GLAO) system which will serve a suite of wide-field near-infrared instruments (ULTIMATE²). Several Canadians have participated in workshops and reviews of this instrument. From these workshops, and informal discussions with members of the instrument team, it has been made clear that Canadian participation would be welcome in the development and construction of this facility.

2.5 Partnership

The user community of Subaru has primarily been Japan, through NAOJ (with some participation from Taiwan and Princeton University who participate significantly through instrumentation projects). International proposals are accepted, and limited exchange time with Gemini has provided some access to Canadians. Canada also led a very fruitful technical collaboration to bring the multi-object AO demonstrator, RAVEN, to Subaru (Andersen et al., 2012; Lamb et al., 2017). However, as the need to support TMT operations ramps up, Subaru's operations budget is being significantly reduced, and NAOJ is required to find international partners to keep the telescope operational. This will require a transformation of the Observatory's governance as well, into a full international partnership. This provides an opportunity for Canada to gain significant and critical access to this facility at an opportune time, as described in § 3.

NAOJ has been discussing partnership scenarios with potential partners, including Canada, for a couple of years. In particular, an NAOJ delegation presented a preliminary partnership model at the [Wide Field Astronomy in Canada](#) workshop held at the Perimeter Institute in 2018. Though this model has evolved somewhat since that meeting, one constant has been that the number of science nights available will scale directly with the level of contribution, both cash and in-kind. In the most recent description this amounts to approximately \$86,000 USD per science night (i.e. excluding weather and engineering time). Two types of partnership are envisaged: Partners and Associates. Partners require a contribution of at least \$2M USD per year in cash, for at least three years. In addition, in-kind contributions totalling no more than 25% of the partner's cash contribution may be counted toward the share of observing time. Partners are able to apply for both Intensive Programs (5-40 nights) and Large Programs³ (more than 40 nights), as well as regular PI proposals. They are also able to participate in all decision-making processes, including a seat on the Board, the Subaru Science Advisory Committee (SSAC) and the Time Allocation Committee (TAC). The second category is that of Associates who can join for a smaller contribution, of at least \$0.4M/year (2 year minimum). Unlike Partners, Associates do not have a role in governance, and cannot participate in Large Programs.

The instrument that is likely to be of most interest to many Canadians is PFS. New partners will be able to propose to use PFS, including for new, Large Programs. However, Subaru partnership does not in itself enable participation in the SSP, expected to be ≥ 300 nights, that will be allocated to the PFS consortium as compensation for providing the instrument. Particularly for cosmological applications, the PFS SSP has the potential to achieve some very high impact science that will be difficult to surpass with subsequent PFS surveys. For this reason, engagement with this first SSP is of prime importance for several Canadians. There may remain opportunities to negotiate access to the PFS SSP, though the window for this is closing as we approach the start of PFS operations. Negotiation for participation in the PFS SSP is not with NAOJ but with the PFS partnership, although NAOJ has expressed interest in helping with this negotiation as part of its goal of recruiting Canada as a Subaru partner.

²Ultra-wide Laser Tomographic Imager and MOS with AO for Transcendent Exploration (ULTIMATE-Subaru): <https://ultimate.naoj.org/english/instrument.html>

³The detailed concept of the Large Program has not been determined yet, but it is planned to be set up as a different large project category from the SSP category.

Figure 1: An approximate timeline showing Canadian OIR facilities on the ground (blue for current facilities, and green for those that are yet to come) and in space (red). Euclid and LSST are internationally-led projects dedicated to imaging surveys. While Canada does not have a national participation in Euclid, a significant number of Canadians are involved; efforts are underway to enable national (or at least broad Canadian) LSST participation, through CFI. TMT and MSE are ambitious facilities that will secure Canadian leadership in OIR astronomy, but they will not see first light much before 2030. In the meantime, access to Subaru would be the perfect fit to prepare for MSE (scientifically and technically), to find targets for TMT and JWST, to strengthen the TMT partnership and to build toward a coherent Maunakea Observatory.

3 Strategic alignment: Subaru as a bridge to the future

Subaru will remain the dominant wide field imager in the northern hemisphere for at least a decade. Moreover, with PFS it will host the only 8-m class, wide field OIR spectrograph until MSE.

In addition to its intrinsic scientific value, Subaru access provides a number of strategic advantages, including:

- MSE is an ambitious, international project of which Canada is currently the leader, with first light expected in 2029 in a technically paced schedule. To capitalize on their MSE investment, Canadians will need to be ready to obtain, calibrate and exploit the massive amounts of exquisite data that MSE will deliver. However, we are currently not engaged in any large spectroscopic surveys at the national level, and haven't been for nearly twenty years. Therefore, it will be challenging to ramp up the Canadian community to the needed level without access to pathfinder instrumentation of comparable complexity. PFS on Subaru is the perfect example of such a pathfinder, with similar specifications to MSE. Indeed, in the next decade, PFS is poised to take the first look at some of the important science questions MSE will address definitively. Experience gained through engagement with PFS and its surveys will help Canadians lead the design, construction and exploitation of MSE, and will get the Canadian community involved in the exciting science that will come from these facilities.
- TMT represents the next big leap in OIR astronomy, with sensitivity > 100 times greater than current telescopes for many applications. Given its relatively small field of view, TMT will largely rely on deep imaging and spectroscopic surveys from 8-m class telescopes to identify interesting targets. HSC and PFS are likely to be the very best facilities to provide such surveys. Japan is a large TMT partner, and there is a great deal of scientific overlap between our astronomy communities. Partnering with Japan now allows us to build technical and scientific collaborations that will let us make the best use of our TMT access in the future.
- Subaru plans a GLAO-fed, wide-field NIR imager as their next bright-time instrument under the ULTIMATE umbrella. This has the potential to provide an interesting complement to Euclid and JWST. Canadian involvement now would give us the opportunity to help shape development of this capability, or perhaps bring new ideas to the table (e.g. a NIR MOS as a MSE pathfinder).
- Stronger collaboration between our partners on Maunakea has the potential for operational cost-savings in the future. It is also an important first step toward a formal alliance of observatories that is practically, and scientifically, needed to maximize our investment in these facilities.

Figure 3 shows how access to Subaru in the 2020s would bridge the gap to MSE and TMT, providing the necessary access to deep, wide field imaging necessary to capitalize on our investment with JWST and Euclid.

4 Proposed Share and Resourcing

Access to Subaru can have a transformative impact on present and future Canadian astronomy, but only if we have access to Large Programs, and a voice in governance, to take advantage of Subaru's ability to conduct surveys. With a minimum contribution of \$2M per year, Canada would have access to about 24 nights per year. This is just less than 25% of the time Canada currently gets on Gemini⁴ and, as such, is likely to be heavily oversubscribed. In particular, to really take advantage of Subaru's survey capabilities, Canada will want to lead and participate in Large Programs, consisting of 40 nights or more. With 24 nights per year in partner time, building a substantial Large Program will likely require multipartner proposals (which is a good thing, as building partnership with the Japanese is one of the goals), and a coordinated effort within Canada. A larger share would certainly be put to good use. If appropriate in-kind contributions could be identified, the share could be increased to about 30 nights per year without additional cash. A smaller share, as a Subaru Associate Member, would not be without value, but it would not likely result in a significant impact relative to current activity.

Part of the motivation for this partnership is as preparation for work with future facilities (MSE, TMT, JWST etc) and, as such, any funding provided should not have a negative impact on those ambitions. Instead, this should be new money seen as an investment toward maximizing success of those projects, as well as with the more immediate effect of enhancing the scientific discovery led by Canadians in the next decade. While it might be possible to consider a corresponding future reduction in the share of our other 8-m facility (Gemini), the recent Assessment Point consultation demonstrated interest in Gemini remains high, particularly given its strategic planning for LSST followup (South) and adaptive optics optimization (North). Subaru offers capabilities Gemini does not, and therefore participation in both provides an important diversification, increasing the scientific capabilities to which Canadians have access and the breadth of the community that is served. Nevertheless, if funding cannot be found to join Subaru while maintaining our current Gemini share, reallocating some funding from Gemini to Subaru should be considered. Alternatively, or in addition, reduction of our share in CFHT could be considered. For most wide-field imaging applications Subaru+HSC gives a much better \$/photon ratio than CFHT+MegaCam. This is particularly true in the time period between the conclusion of the current CFHT Large Programs, and start of MSE construction, where CFHT will struggle to be competitive.

It is important to some Canadians that such a partnership also include participation in the PFS SSP. This will require further negotiation, beyond NAOJ. The PFS instrument team is in fact looking for cash contributions now, at a rate of about \$5M for 10 faculty to join the SSP.

5 Summary and recommendations

A new partnership with Subaru is timely, scientifically compelling and strategically important. Even a five year partnership would allow us to develop the collaborations, skills and expertise we need to make the most of our involvement in TMT and MSE, and to bridge the gap to these facilities as CFHT becomes non-competitive. We recommend that:

- Canada negotiate participation as a full Subaru partner for an initial period of three years. While a \$2M/year (10%) contribution is the minimum, a larger share would best position Canada to lead and participate in the Large Programs that fully exploit Subaru's survey capability.
- Funding for this opportunity to bridge the time before start of MSE operations should be new money, and not impact any of our future ambitions (e.g. MSE, TMT). In-kind contributions should be sought to increase the share by the maximum amount acceptable to NAOJ. If new money cannot be found, a reduction of share in CFHT and/or Gemini should be made.

⁴In 2019B and 2020A Canada has almost exactly 1000 hours on the two Gemini telescopes combined.

- Partnership negotiation should be done in parallel with the PFS collaboration, so that it can include a mechanism for at least some Canadians to participate in the first PFS SSP(s).

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Wide field imaging and spectroscopy on a large telescope is a unique capability that will lead to transformational advances in cosmology, galaxy and black hole formation in numerous ways. Naturally, numerous HSC and PFS targets will be perfect for follow-up with future facilities (e.g. JWST and TMT). Some examples of the tremendous science potential include:

- Takada et al. (2014) describes the science case for a 300 night PFS survey. This includes Dark energy constraints via baryonic acoustic oscillation and redshift distortion measurements; assembly histories of the Milky Way and M31 via radial velocities and chemical abundances of stars; and a SDSS-like survey of the galaxy and AGN population at $1 < z < 2$.
- The HSC-SSP fields are rich in ancillary data, including new and ongoing CFHT u-band, Spitzer IRAC, and eRosita x-ray observations (Sawicki et al., 2019; Mehta et al., 2018; Sajina et al., 2018). Almost 25% of the HSC SSP dataset is publicly available as of May 2019, allowing astronomers across the globe to explore all aspects of Wide and Deep/Ultradeep surveys. With access to PFS and HSC, Canadian astronomers would be in a privileged position to propose and/or join ambitious follow-up observations (e.g. narrow-band imaging in sections of the Wide survey and/or wide-field spectroscopy) of HSC SSP targets on Subaru.
- HSC is already providing enormous new samples of, e.g., high redshift galaxies and low surface brightness galaxies across a range of environments; populations that hold keys to outstanding questions of galaxy evolution. Publicly released deep HSC SSP (DR2, Aihara et al., 2019) imaging ($i \sim 26$ of 300 deg^2 and $i \sim 26.7$ of 35 deg^2) with superb seeing ($0.6''$ on average in i band) enables studies of galaxy mass assembly at $z < 2$ through star formation and merging processes (via the evolution of the stellar mass function, galaxy pair statistics, and analysis of low surface brightness galaxy outskirts) and determination of the stellar-to-halo mass ratio (from galaxy-galaxy lensing and angular clustering).
- HSC is well-suited for tracing Lyman-alpha emitters and Lyman-break galaxies at redshift $2 < z < 9$ by a combination of broad and narrow-band imaging. In addition to characterizing star formation and stellar populations of high-redshift galaxies, these datasets include large samples of proto-clusters, providing new constraints on structure formation.
- Augmented by redshift surveys carried out with the PFS, HSC imaging will be used for studies of the dark matter distribution, and to probe the nature of dark energy.
- The sensitivity and field of view of HSC enables the search for the faintest galaxies in the Local Group as well as mapping of the Milky Way halo.

In addition to the wide field science described above, we note that the search for life outside our solar system is one of the last frontiers in astronomy. Key instrument progress in wavefront sensing and high-contrast systems is expected in the next decade to bring us closer to this fundamental discovery. Subaru's SCExAO is leading the way for validating new technologies to boost performance and enable new breakthrough science. Having a higher share in Subaru would enable stronger Canadian participation in the project and access to unique science capabilities, positioning Canada at the forefront of the field for the next decade. The knowledge acquired from SCExAO is key to developing state-of-the-art VLOT instruments. Key new science opportunities that goes beyond the capabilities of the current GPI and SPHERE instruments are expected from SCExAO, from the

characterization of the reflected light of known radial velocity planets, to the discovery of young solar system analogs, to forming gas giant planets in nearby star forming regions. SCExAO-like capabilities on a VLOT will enable the search and characterization of the reflected light of Earth-mass planets in the habitable zone of the nearest M-dwarfs, the detection in the NIR emission of young Saturn-mass planets around nearby young stars, and the 10 micron imaging discovery and characterization of Earth-mass planets in the habitable zone around nearby Sun-like stars.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The Board, Science Advisory Committee and Time Allocation Committee will all be constituted such that seats appointed by the NAOJ Director General will comprise the majority. There is therefore a small scientific risk that scientific programs and initiatives important to Canadians do not succeed because they do not resonate with our partners. This risk is likely most important for Large Programs and future instrumentation initiatives. It is, however, not significantly different from the situation we face on Gemini, ALMA, or any other facility for which we do not have a majority share. It can be mitigated by appointing good, knowledgeable people to the relevant committees.

With a \$2M/year contribution, Canada would have access to about 24 nights per year. Participation in Large Programs will likely require coordination within Canada and with international partners to carry out ambitious proposals (~ 100 nights). Our ability to maximize the impact of Subaru access will depend to some extent on our ability to organize around science themes of national interest. Canadians do have a good history of doing this, most recently demonstrated with CFIS/UNIONS.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

As one of a small number of partners on the Board, Canada would have input into the scientific direction of Subaru. There would certainly be the opportunity to lead scientific investigations, including Large Programs (including surveys). While Subaru is anticipating a limited instrumentation suite, there is currently scope to participate in defining and building the next, NIR, capability. An important feature of this envisioned instrument is the GLAO and associated instrument suite (ULTIMATE), for which we have considerable interest and expertise in Canada. For example, there could be an opportunity for Canada to lead the development of a multi-object NIR spectrograph, which would also serve as a prototype for one of the MSE spectrographs.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Serious discussions about possible partnership emerged in early 2019, and in a series of email and videoconference discussions we obtained expressions of interest from nearly 30 Canadian astronomers with a wide range of scientific expertise. Many of these are coauthors on this white paper as a show of support.

A small amount of time on Subaru has been available to Canada via Gemini exchange time, since 2015. Demand has been strong, usually with between 10 and 40 hours requested each semester, and for a wide range of instruments. This certainly underestimates the demand for ambitious programs with HSC, PFS or SCExAO, which would require far more time than could be made available through the exchange route.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

There are many important strategic synergies for the Canadian community, including:

- Subaru and TMT: HSC and PFS are perfectly suited to provide targets for follow-up with the Thirty Metre Telescope (TMT). Japan is a large TMT partner, of similar “weight” to Canada, and a collaboration with them now allows us to develop technical and scientific collaborations that will let us make the best use of our TMT access in the next decade and beyond. Importantly, with their wide fields of view, HSC and PFS will be perfect for identifying rare, exceptionally interesting objects for follow-up with TMT, given identical sky coverage.
- Subaru and MSE: MSE is an ambitious international project that Canada currently leads. To capitalize on MSE we need to be ready to obtain, reduce, and exploit the massive amounts of exquisite data that MSE will deliver. However, Canada is currently not engaged in any large spectroscopic surveys at the national level, and hasn’t been for nearly twenty years. Consequently, it will be challenging to ramp up our community to the level needed to lead the construction and scientific exploitation of MSE without access to pathfinder instrumentation of comparable complexity. PFS on Subaru is the perfect such pathfinder. In the next decade, PFS is already poised to take the first look at some of the important science questions that MSE will address definitively. Experience with PFS surveys now will allow Canadians to continue to lead the design, construction and - critically - scientific exploitation of MSE in the future.
- Future Subaru instrumentation: Subaru plans a GLAO-fed instrument suite (ULTIMATE). The instrument suite, the first of which will be a GLAO-fed NIR imager, has the potential to provide interesting complementarity to Euclid and JWST. Canada will have the opportunity to influence the design of this instrument and to bring new ideas to the table (e.g., a NIR MOS, which could also serve as an MSE pathfinder instrument). All this would provide great instrument development opportunities to HAA and university labs.
- Maunakea partnership: ESO has very clearly demonstrated the power of large partnerships in modern astronomy. While it has been shown that it is impractical for Canada to join ESO, developing a strong alliance of observatories on Maunakea has the potential for dramatically increasing scientific impact and reducing cost through optimally combining our strengths. Joining Subaru now is the next step towards building such an alliance.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

For most wide-field imaging applications, Subaru/HSC is about nine times more efficient than CFHT/MegaCam. The \$86k/night cost of Subaru would easily outperform our current investment in CFHT in this regard.

Gemini-N and Subaru are both 8m telescopes in the same geographic location. In many ways joining Subaru can be viewed as extending our use of Gemini to include other instrumentation — specifically instrumentation requiring access to a wide field of view. The cost-per-night proposed by Subaru (\$86k) includes a contribution to “sunk” costs of construction, and is therefore higher than what Canada pays for the operation of Gemini, which is about \$55k per night per telescope and which does not include the sunk construction costs of Gemini. The Subaru per night cost is, however, comparable to what Gemini has charged others for similar partnership models in recent years. Note that access to more time through multi-partner programs (including for Large Programs), can bring down the effective cost per night. Additional benefits on top of the basic partnership (e.g. participation in the PFS SSP) would make the deal even more attractive.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

One of the motivations for pursuing this partnership is the synergy with TMT and MSE, and the close co-

ordination between observatories on Maunakea for the purpose of providing a diverse suite of capabilities to a Canadian community with increasingly broad interests. As is well described in other white papers, the future of both TMT and MSE remains uncertain. This does not affect the great scientific benefits that will be obtained from Subaru access directly. Moreover, facilities similar to TMT and MSE will certainly be built, somewhere. Given its latitude, there is even substantial overlap with the sky coverage of Chilean observatories from Maunakea. Subaru access will provide an important complement that could be helpful in allowing Canadians to participate in, or collaborate with, those facilities.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Subaru partnership provides an opportunity for industry to build future instrumentation (e.g., as part of ULTIMATE). But most critically it provides a route to train HQP in the field of wide-field survey astronomy. Both imaging and spectroscopic surveys will dominate the future for many fields of astrophysics. With MSE, Canada has taken the conceptual lead for wide-field spectroscopy in the 2030s, but we risk not having the expertise to capitalize on this initiative because we have virtually no direct access to resources for training the next generation in this area. Subaru would fill that need and ensure that those HQP are well prepared to lead the world with MSE.

References

- Aihara, H., Arimoto, N., Armstrong, R., et al. 2018, PASJ, 70, S4
- Aihara, H., AlSayyad, Y., Ando, M., et al. 2019, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1905.12221
- Andersen, D. R., Jackson, K. J., Blain, C., et al. 2012, PASP, 124, 469
- Aoki, W., Arimoto, N., Sadakane, K., et al. 2009, A&A, 502, 569
- Cirasuolo, M., Afonso, J., Bender, R., et al. 2012, in Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, Vol. 8446, Proc. SPIE, 84460S
- Dalton, G., Trager, S. C., Abrams, D. C., et al. 2012, in Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, Vol. 8446, Proc. SPIE, 84460P
- DESI Collaboration, Aghamousa, A., Aguilar, J., et al. 2016, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1611.00037
- Gerard, B. L., Marois, C., & Galicher, R. 2018, AJ, 156, 106
- Graur, O., Poznanski, D., Maoz, D., et al. 2011, MNRAS, 417, 916
- Hamana, T., Miyazaki, S., Shimasaku, K., et al. 2003, ApJ, 597, 98
- Haynes, R., Barden, S., de Jong, R., et al. 2014, in Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series, Vol. 9147, Proc. SPIE, 91476I
- Ibata, R. A., McConnachie, A., Cuillandre, J.-C., et al. 2017, ApJ, 848, 128
- Koda, J., Yagi, M., Yamanoi, H., & Komiyama, Y. 2015, ApJ, 807, L2
- Kodama, T., Smail, I., Nakata, F., Okamura, S., & Bower, R. G. 2001, ApJ, 562, L9
- Kong, X., Daddi, E., Arimoto, N., et al. 2006, ApJ, 638, 72
- Kovács, O. E., Bogdán, Á., & Canning, R. E. A. 2019, ApJ, 879, L12
- Lamb, M., Venn, K., Andersen, D., et al. 2017, MNRAS, 465, 3536
- Lilly, S. J., Le Fevre, O., Hammer, F., & Crampton, D. 1996, ApJ, 460, L1
- Matsuoka, Y., Onoue, M., Kashikawa, N., et al. 2016, ApJ, 828, 26
- McConnachie, A. W., Arimoto, N., & Irwin, M. 2007, MNRAS, 379, 379
- Mehta, V., Scarlata, C., Capak, P., et al. 2018, ApJS, 235, 36
- Niikura, H., Takada, M., Yasuda, N., et al. 2019, Nature Astronomy, 3, 524
- Ono, Y., Ouchi, M., Harikane, Y., et al. 2018, PASJ, 70, S10
- Ouchi, M., Shimasaku, K., Akiyama, M., et al. 2008, ApJS, 176, 301

- Sajina, A., Bezanson, R., Capak, P., et al. 2018, Adding the missing piece: Spitzer imaging of the HSC-Deep/PFS fields, Cycle 14 Spitzer Program #14081
- Sawicki, M., Arnouts, S., Huang, J., et al. 2019, MNRAS, 489, 5202
- Smee, S. A., Barkhouser, R. H., & Glazebrook, K. 2006, in Proc. SPIE, Vol. 6269, 62692I
- Takada, M., Ellis, R. S., Chiba, M., et al. 2014, PASJ, 66, R1
- Umetsu, K., Medezinski, E., Nonino, M., et al. 2014, ApJ, 795, 163
- Yee, H. K. C., Ellingson, E., & Carlberg, R. G. 1996, ApJS, 102, 269